

A short Guideline for Open Data Publishing

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Open Data for a Digital Future of Science

Open data is not only a requirement of many projects, institutions and funding agencies, but also ensures the highest value that can be generated for the data for science. Openly published data can supplement a publication and generates visibility for the researcher, as it can be cited like any other publication. Furthermore, it also allows sharing data that is often not available in publications, such as negative experimental results that can prevent the duplication of work and are crucial for new digital approaches in science such as AI.

Nevertheless, while open publication is desirable, the published data also needs to be FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) to retain its value and remain understandable independent from individual researchers or institutions. In this guideline, we aim to provide a convenient starting point to publish data in a FAIR and open way.

Standalone Data or Linked Data?

Standalone data uploads are not directly linked a publication. To make these data uploads understandable for all researchers, all necessary information needs to be provided together with the dataset. For example, a performance data set of a catalyst (e.g. yield over time) in a model reaction is not understandable without stating the structure of the catalyst and the chosen model reaction. To make the data findable and citable, a unique persistent identifier for the data can be provided by the repository.

On the other hand, data linked to a publication must be understandable in conjunction with the publication. Using the same example as above, the performance data set may now be uploaded without stating the catalyst structure or model reaction, as this information will be available in the publication. Linking the data to a publication is very easy: State the publisher, DOI and name of the linked publication in the description of the data set and use "Dataset for the publication: XXXX" as the title when uploading the data. When submitting the publication, simply state the persistent identifier for the respective dataset. Repositories allow to reserve persistent identifiers even if the data is not uploaded yet. Keep in mind that services such as DataCite allow to track the connection between a publication and a dataset if the persistent identifier is provided after the submission of the publication. Accordingly, it is also possible to upload linked data retrospectively.

With this differentiation in mind, the following minimum requirements for open data uploads should be followed for linked data. Additionally, in case of standalone data, the readme-file needs to include all required information for understanding and reproducing experiments.

Minimum Requirements for Open Data Uploads

- All data that is necessary to recreate the figures in the original paper should be uploaded.
- Sort the data in separate folders either by experimental method or figure number corresponding to the data in the publication. Include at least one readme-file, which should serve as guide to the user for understanding the uploaded dataset(s).
- The readme-file (as .txt) must include necessary information about the data, e.g. previous data processing or explanation of sample abbreviations. It should also guide which data can be found in which folder. Experimental conditions do not have to be repeated if already sufficiently described in the paper. If larger amounts of description and metadata must be stated to fully

understand the dataset, separate readmes can be included in the subfolders for specific methods. For convenience, the separate readmes can be referred to in the general readme, e.g. "Folder IR: IR-Spectra from XXX experiments including description can be found in "IR-Readme""

- File names should be understandable (no undefined abbreviations). 25 characters should not be exceeded for the file name. If not possible, e.g. for sample names, an explanation of abbreviations should be included in the readme.
- Files should be uploaded as non-proprietary format, e.g. .csv or .txt, to allow reuse without specific commercial software. Calculations can be added as separate excel-files. Ideally, state in the readme or directly in the excel-file which decimal divider is used (. or ,) to avoid confusion.
- Files should be unaltered raw data if possible. Conversion of the raw data to an open format should still be done for accessibility. Any alterations of the raw data should be documented in the readme.
- Depending on the method, required information for understanding and reproducing experiments might have to be included as readme if not directly available in the linked publication. This is especially important for standalone datasets.
- Scripts for data analysis, e.g. in Python, should be included. Provide a link in the readme if these already uploaded on other platforms like GitHub or GitLab.
- To ensure interoperability, all information regarding creator of the data, provenance, related project, funding statements and potential restrictions for reuse need to be included in the description of the data set.
- For broad possibilities of reuse, open data should be uploaded under a CC BY 4.0 license, which permits all reuse as long as the original author is credited.

To further enhance your datasets, any additional data not represented as figures in the linked publication can be added as additional folders. Keep in mind that an additional description for understanding of the data in the readme might be necessary if not all information is already provided in the linked publication